

Direct determination of arsenic in high salinity samples by graphite furnace atomic absorption spectrometry

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Abstract:

Negative impact on the environment caused by heavy metals contamination is of interest to many ecotoxicological studies. Arsenic is present naturally in the water and soil ecosystems due to the weathering and eroding of rocks and soil. However, arsenic compounds released into the environment from anthropogenic sources (e.g., fertilizers and pesticides, combustion of fossil fuels and mining activities) can cause permanent damage to human health (Wang et al., 2014). The contamination of the environment by heavy metals reduces the hygienic quality of foodstuffs. Generally, the arsenic threatens the population through contaminated drinking water sources. Also fruits, fruit juices, and grains are among the primary dietary sources of inorganic arsenic exposure, especially in regions with high arsenic concentration in water. Due to the method of cultivation, rice is able to bioaccumulate 10-fold higher of arsenic than other grains such as wheat and barley (Cao et al., 2018; Cubadda et al., 2017). Determination of total arsenic content in aqueous samples is usually performed by graphite furnace atomic absorption spectrometry (GF-AAS). However, determination of arsenic concentration in high salinity samples (e.g. seawater, mineralized water) may be complicated by losses of the analyte during the pyrolysis stage and interferences caused by sample matrix (Bermejo-Barrera et al., 1996; Bozsai et al., 1990; Welz et al. 1988). To achieve better results, the temperature program of the GF-AAS method is usually modified. Some researchers also use the surface-modified graphite tubes (Volynsky, 1998).

In this study, the sensitive and precise method for the determination of arsenic in samples containing high chlorides concentration was optimized. The standard arsenic solution ($50 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) in solution NaCl (10 g L^{-1}) was used for method optimization. High concentration of sodium chloride in the sample matrix caused high background absorbance which deformed the absorbance of the arsenic. To reduce the background absorption a cool-down step was incorporated into the graphite furnace temperature program before the atomization step. Although we have achieved very good results of arsenic recovery through temperature program improvement, the lifetime of the graphite tube was reduced due to the aggressive composition of the sample matrix. The surface of the graphite tube was significantly damaged after about 50 firing cycles. For this reason, we have combined the cool-down step temperature program with the modification of graphite furnace surface by tungsten carbides (using the aqueous solution Na_2WO_4 (Figure 1)).

Figure 1: Graphite furnace surface-modification procedure

Thanks to the combination of graphite furnace temperature program with the cool-down pre-atomization step and graphite tube modified with tungsten carbides, the background absorbance was reduced about 95–100%. The new methodology allowed the determination of arsenic in solution NaCl (10 g L^{-1}) with the recovery of 98–100%. Limit of detection was decreased 11.3 times and the lifetime of the graphite tube was increased five times. Moreover, standard addition calibration method instead of matrix-free calibration was used to reduction matrix interferences. This step improved the performance of the methodology and made it independent of the knowledge of the NaCl concentration in the sample.

Keywords: arsenic, GF-AAS, palladium modifier, tungsten carbides

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References

- Bermejo-Barrera, P., Moreda-Piñeiro, J., Moreda-Piñeiro, A., & Bermejo-Barrera, A. (1996). Comparison of different chemical modifiers for the direct determination of arsenic in sea water by electrothermal atomic absorption spectrometry. *Fresenius' journal of analytical chemistry*, 355(2), 174-179.
- Bozsai, G., Schlemmer, G., & Grobanski, Z. (1990). Determination of arsenic, cadmium, lead and selenium in highly mineralized waters by graphite-furnace atomic-absorption spectrometry. *Talanta*, 37(6), 545-553.

- Cao, H., Xie, X., Wang, Y., Pi, K., Li, J., Zhan, H., & Liu, P. (2018). Predicting the risk of groundwater arsenic contamination in drinking water wells. *Journal of Hydrology*, 560, 318-325.
- Cubadda, F., Jackson, B. P., Cottingham, K. L., Van Horne, Y. O., & Kurzius-Spencer, M. (2017). Human exposure to dietary inorganic arsenic and other arsenic species: State of knowledge, gaps and uncertainties. *Science of the total environment*, 579, 1228-1239.
- Volynsky, A. (1998). Graphite atomizers modified with high-melting carbides for electrothermal atomic absorption spectrometry. II. Practical aspects. *Spectrochimica Acta Part B: Atomic Spectroscopy*, 53(12), 1607-1644.
- Wang, P., Sun, G., Jia, Y., Meharg, A. A., & Zhu, Y. (2014). A review on completing arsenic biogeochemical cycle: microbial volatilization of arsines in environment. *Journal of Environmental Sciences*, 26(2), 371-381.
- Welz, B., Schlemmer, G., & Mudakavi, J. R. (1988). Palladium nitrate-magnesium nitrate modifier for graphite furnace atomic absorption spectrometry. Part 2. Determination of arsenic, cadmium, copper, manganese, lead, antimony, selenium and thallium in water. *Journal of Analytical Atomic Spectrometry*, 3(5), 695-701.